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Writing the Sovereign Self: Representation and Reconfiguration of Female Sovereignty in Nawab Sultan Jahan Begam's *An Account of My Life* (1912)

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Abstract:

This article examines Nawab Sultan Jahan Begam's *An Account of My Life* (1912) to delineate how she employs her autobiography as a site for representing and reconfiguring existent discourses on female sovereignty. Sultan Jahan Begam was the last of the four successive female rulers who ruled the erstwhile princely state of Bhopal for over a century. The article traces how the Begam, by drawing upon a varied lineage of influences from Mughal imperial self-representation to modern modes of self-narration, and creating a narrative niche of a legendary female tradition, represents herself as a ruler in late colonial India. In doing so, it unravels the royal woman's self-fashioning through a strategic utilisation of her position as sovereign to redefine the dynamics between gender and power in a predominantly patriarchal socio-political context.

Keywords: Princely states, female sovereignty, autobiography, Sultan Jahan Begam, power.

Introduction

In the colonial era, two-fifths of the Indian subcontinent was divided into over six hundred individual princely states, which were governed by regional rulers in a subsidiary alliance with the British Raj (Ernst and Pati 1). After India's political independence, the initiation of democratic rule and the merging of the princely states with the Indian union terminated the princely era. The existing scholarship on Indian princely states focuses predominantly on the *maharajas*, the socio-political aspects of the states in the context of colonial rule (Jeffrey 1978; Copland 1997; Kooiman 2002; Ramusack 2005; Allen 2005; Keen 2012), with comparatively limited research conducted on the elite and non-elite women in princely states. Angma Dey Jhala points out that the courtly Indian woman was, in fact, a "principal actor and potent symbol in Indian society and history" who played a significant role in matters of state succession, alliances and governance (Jhala 3). Many of them, like the Begums of Bhopal, Sethu Lakshmi Bai of Travancore and Indira Devi of Cooch Behar, among others, held positions of authority as rulers and regents of prominent princely states. However, the power exercised by them was subject to various restrictions owing to their positions as imperial subjects as well as women in a patriarchal system. A critical enquiry into their engagement with discourses of power and the strategies they employed to exercise agency within this framework can be crucial while mapping out the gendered negotiations of power in late colonial India. The power and agency exercised by these elite women also need to be reassessed, especially in the context of their problematisation by Feminist and Subaltern scholars (Chakravarti 1989; Guru 1995; Rege 2005). Autobiographies are particularly suited for this investigation since first-person life narratives have always been crucial in "unveiling a significant layer of historical experience" (Kumar 293).

In this context, the article examines the autobiography of Nawab Sultan Jahan Begam of Bhopal, titled *An Account of My Life* (1912), to delineate how she employs her

autobiography as a site for representing and reconfiguring discourses on female sovereignty in late colonial India. Autobiography facilitates the entwining of an individual's personal narrative with the larger political and historical narrative of the society she lives in. The implications of this are particularly pronounced for women occupying positions of power. A close reading of Sultan Jahan Begum's autobiography delineates how she manoeuvred the mazes of patriarchy and power. It also unravels the extent to which her expression of self-perception and subjectivity was dictated by her role in the public and private spheres. The strategies employed by her to navigate the cultural constraints and the modern state's protocols in the colonial context to challenge the existing narratives of gendered self is another point of enquiry in this article.

An Account of My Life: The Text and the Context

Sultan Jahan Begam was the Nawab of the princely state of Bhopal in central India from 1901 to 1926 and was the last of the four successive female rulers who ruled Bhopal for over a century. The female rule in Bhopal began in 1819 when Qudsia Begam, the Nawab's widow, took over the charge of the State after the death of her husband. Later, Qudsia Begam declared her daughter Nawab Sikandar Begam as her heir; the latter ruled the state of Bhopal, first as regent from 1844 to 1860, then as full-fledged Nawab from 1860 to 1868. After Sikandar Begam's death in 1868, her daughter Shah Jahan Begam became the Nawab, who was later succeeded by her daughter Sultan Jahan Begam (Khan 2000; Lambert Hurley 2007). While such a matriarchal succession was an exception among the princely states in India, it was supported by the British due to strategic reasons. In return for the British support, the Begams of Bhopal remained loyal to the colonial government and Bhopal emerged as a prominent princely state in the late colonial era. Moreover, though these Begams married, they remained the rulers of the state by their own right instead of handing over the position to their husbands

(as was the patriarchal custom). This legacy of female sovereignty had a significant influence on Sultan Jahan Begam's autobiographical self-fashioning as a ruler.

An Account of My Life (1912) is the English translation of Sultan Jahan Begam's autobiography *Gauhar-e-Iqbal* originally written in Urdu. It was translated by C. H. Payne, who was the education advisor to the Begam. The Begam also wrote *Akhtar-e-Iqbal*, which is the second part of *Gauhar-e-Iqbal* and covers the later period of the Begam's reign. *An Account of My Life* is divided into two parts—the first part gives an account of the times of her grandmother and mother, covering the period up to Sultan Jahan's ascension as the Nawab. The second part provides a detailed picture of her reign till the year 1904.

Though referred to as an autobiography, *An Account of My Life* is a peculiar life narrative in many ways. From the style to the structure and the content, it shows influences ranging from Mughal imperial self-representation to modern modes of self-narration. This conscious confluence of different traditions and its significance in the self-fashioning of a female ruler merits further study, especially considering that the Begam and her predecessors occupied this position in a predominantly patriarchal socio-political context that was not favourable for female sovereignty.

The peculiarity of the text is evident from its introductory chapter where Sultan Jahan Begam describes her autobiography as an attempt “to complete the history of Bhopal down to the present time” (Begam 1), thereby enmeshing her own life with the history of her state. While the dominant Western model of autobiography perceives autobiography as the expression of an individual self (Gusdorf 1980; Olney 1980), many Indian autobiographies have challenged this paradigm (Kumar 23). In the case of Sultan Jahan, rather than as an expression of the inner self as projected by the Western model of autobiography, her life narrative is envisioned as instrumental in forging a link between an illustrious past and a

promising future of Bhopal by recording the state's past and making it available for her successors. These aspects highlight her public role as a sovereign and her duty as the inheritor of a glorious legacy, rather than foregrounding her individual, inner self. The employment of the genre of autobiography for this purpose, I argue, indicates a peculiar perception and presentation of the self – a self that is inseparably interwoven with the history and tradition of a state, which would further validate her position as the ruler of the state.

This notion is further reinforced in various parts of the book. In the introductory chapter, Sultan Jahan writes about the intended readers who can benefit from her book. The primary intended beneficiaries are the future generations who, according to her, could use it as a reference regarding domestic and public duties. Interestingly, the Begam's act of writing her life narrative as a source of guidance to her successors and as a continuation of her predecessors' works functions as a matrilineal counterpart of the Mughal tradition of maintaining a patrilineal biographical record, starting with Babur's *Baburnama*, that was for "their heirs to uphold and served as a form of objectified counsel" (Bokhari 165). However, this adoption of the Mughal mode of imperial self-fashioning is not an exception in the case of Sultan Jahan Begam. Her mother, Shah Jahan Begam, who was named after the fifth Mughal emperor, commissioned gardens, palaces and a grand mosque, designed to emulate the style of the Mughals. She also wrote a book, among others, titled *Taj-ul Iqbal Tárikh Bhopal*, or, *The History of Bhopal* (1876), where she linked her regime to the Mughal state. Also, Sultan Jahan, in her autobiography, likens her grandmother Sikandar Begam's role in Bhopal to that of Akbar in the Mughal empire, drawing parallels between both the rulers' administrative efficiency during "critical" times (Begam 5). This inclusion of Mughal symbols, Metcalf argues, "offered a claim on grandeur along with a place on the emerging national stage experienced through the new category of colonial 'princes'" (14). In that sense, the Begam rulers of Bhopal, given their

religious affiliation, incorporated the Mughal element in their self-fashioning to project their regime as bearing the legacy of the earlier Islamic dynasty in India known for its glory.

The second category of Sultan Jahan's intended readers is her fellow rulers and political officers in India. She expects that her book would help them to learn from her descriptions of royal durbars and state functions. This declaration implicitly suggests her capability as a seasoned ruler well-versed in matters of the state. Also, many of her descriptions of the durbars, like the imperial durbar at Delhi, explicitly convey her loyalty towards the colonial government. It is also interesting that in the introduction, she presents loyalty to the British as a part of her tradition which needs to be passed on to the future generations: "...and when they read of the brave deeds of their ancestors, of their faithfulness to the British Government, and of the eternal renown which is their reward, I trust it may serve to stir up in their hearts to achieve a similar renown by an ever-increasing loyalty to the same Power..." (1) Hence, through this, she is building her image as a model princely ruler, rooted in her tradition while also expressing her loyalty to the British. It is a reflection of the diplomatic amity she maintained with the colonial government that secured her position as ruler. Furthermore, by presenting the book as a source of guidance for other rulers, she is projecting her mode of governance as a model worthy of emulation by all.

The structure of the book is also of interest here. The narrative begins with a brief history of Bhopal and description of the reigns of Sultan Jahan's notable predecessors. It discusses at length major administrative reforms, political dynamics with the British government, durbars and other official matters, to the extent that it also appears to be a historical text and in certain parts, an administrative manual. However, it does focus on Sultan Jahan's private life, her conjugal relationship and familial conflicts as the narrative progresses, bringing the autobiographical element to the fore. In that sense it combines both the modern form of autobiography and traditional biographical narratives that eulogised particular rulers

and their reign. Such an amalgamation of the traits of different genres also points to the text as a marker of the initial stages of development of the modern autobiography in India.

The Self and the Sovereign: Sultan Jahan Begam's Autobiographical Representation as a Female Ruler

Sultan Jahan Begam's autobiography strategically crafts her image as a female ruler, especially given the rarity of female sovereigns during her time. Though she states in the beginning of her book that she intends to write down the history of Bhopal up to the present time, her emphasis while recounting this history is on extolling the reign of her foremothers, presenting it as the most glorious period of Bhopal's history. In this process, she is not a passive recorder as she sets out to be, but rather, "a creative and active shaper" (Olney 19) of her narrative. By beginning her autobiography with an overview of Bhopal's history that emphasises its earlier female rulers, Sultan Jahan creates a narrative niche of a legendary female tradition within which she places herself.

The Begam draws from various discourses of the time to bolster this tradition of female rule. Employing the discourse of religion, she hails female sovereignty as a proof of divine benevolence by terming it "God's special favour to Bhopal", as "for three successive generations He has placed the reins of government in female hands" (4). The reason for considering this a divine blessing is further elaborated by highlighting the female ruler's abilities as more superior in comparison to that of her male counterparts. She asserts the advantage of having a woman as ruler through the example of her grandmother Sikandar Begam who, besides being "endowed with all the sterner attributes of a ruler" (Begam 4), also possessed the "softer quality, the love of peace and mercy, which only attains its full development in a woman's heart and by which alone true happiness can be spread" (Begam 4). This "softer quality" of the female ruler is shown as an advantageous attribute that men lack,

thereby subverting the stereotypical portrayal of women as lacking in the comparison between sexes, especially in the administration of the state which was considered a predominantly male domain. In another instance, she openly makes a comparison between Sikandar Begam and her grandfather Nawab Wazir Muhammad Khan, both of whom were rulers who twice saved Bhopal from ruin. Jahan remarks, "...let us not forget that the former was a man, and the latter a woman: and that what the man brought about by means of the sword, the woman achieved by a policy of peace and justice" (10). Here again, she projects the woman as a benign ruler who can achieve the same results as a man through more peaceful and just means, which also hints at her being the better administrator. Notably, the so-called feminine virtues are not presented as a compensation for the lack of what are conventionally projected as masculine qualities. Jahan is careful to present the former as an added advantage for a female ruler who also possesses the latter. While acknowledging the gender differences perpetuated in society, Jahan points out that it is possible for a woman to break out of the mould when she writes about Sikandar, "Although a woman, she possessed all the soldierly qualities that distinguished her predecessors" (13). Further vindication of female rule is done through presenting her British contemporary, Queen Victoria, as an ideal monarch whose assumption of power as the Empress of India in 1858, according to the Begam, "brought life and vigour to the fainting East, and dispersing the clouds of ignorance, insecurity, and distrust, spread in their stead the light of peace, progress and knowledge" (21), thereby employing the Orientalist discourse of colonialism.

Sultan Jahan recalls how John Lawrence, the then Viceroy, in the presence of eighty-four ruling Chiefs, spoke of Sikandar Begam as one whose example was worthy of imitation by all rulers of States and argues that "this achievement ... showed to the world that a woman can rise superior to the weaknesses of her sex, and can challenge competition even in those spheres of action which demand qualities that men only are *supposed to possess*" (emphasis

mine, Begam 6). Here again, she challenges the existing practice of attributing certain qualities to a particular gender. By giving a detailed account of the major contributions made by the other three Begams in the different arenas of the State, Sultan Jahan offers substantial evidence for their capability as rulers and expresses her hope of becoming a worthy successor. It is notable that in the chapter after the introduction, she begins with the life story of Nawab Sikandar Begam, her grandmother, instead of starting with her childhood, as is usual in autobiographies. Here also, she underscores her position as the successor of a glorious feminine legacy rather than as an independent individual, signifying her mission as far more immense and profound.

An Account of My Life elaborately describes the rigorous training that Sultan Jahan Begam underwent from her childhood and highlights its significance in moulding her as a ruler. It creates an impression of the level of seriousness and significance attached to the training of the heir, given the extensive range of subjects covered and skillsets developed. The Begam's narrative relates the long process of her becoming a Nawab after years of grooming by the previous rulers, particularly her grandmother Sikandar Begam, thereby implying that it was not merely by accident of birth but rather she was well-qualified to be a ruler.

Sultan Jahan narrates how, from the time of her birth, she was cherished and brought up by her grandmother who declared, "This child is dearer to me than seven sons" (Begam 36), in response to the expectations of the family members to have a male heir. Her education, which began at the age of five, included subjects ranging from Arithmetic to English lessons and fencing practice. There were also daily lessons in reading and translating the Qur'an and training in horse-riding, Persian and Pashtu. Lambert-Hurley notes that this home-training, while unusual among Muslim girls in India at that time, was similar to that imparted to upper-class girls of the same era in Turkey and also comparable to the education received by *sharif* gentlemen of an earlier generation in India. The Pashtu lessons and fencing signified the

Begams' Pathan heritage which was a major aspect of "the cultural identity of Bhopal's nobility" (Lambert- Hurley 26). While thus sustaining her granddaughter's connection to her roots, it can also be seen that Sikandar Begam was far-sighted to add English lessons to Jahan's curriculum, intending to give her an advantage within the colonial system. Besides these, Sikandar Begam often gave practical advice from which Sultan Jahan, as she recalls, derived guidance "both in public and private life" (Begam 40). By thus highlighting her grandmother's intensive engagement in her upbringing from early childhood and the close bond they both shared, Sultan Jahan fashions herself as the true successor of her renowned grandmother's personal and political legacy.

Sultan Jahan's second phase of education, after her grandmother's death, continued under her mother's supervision. She was inducted into practical training with official papers being sent to her by Shah Jahan Begum, to peruse and write orders upon. Thus, the autobiography captures the rigorous training that she underwent, leading up to her accession to the throne. It highlights the time and effort invested by the predecessors and Jahan herself in ensuring that she was equipped enough to meet the demands of statesmanship. This aligns to her previously stated objective of presenting a model for her successors; moreover, it implies that proper education and guidance are significant in the making of a competent ruler, compared to which gender is irrelevant.

Sultan Jahan Begam's autobiography also engages with the discourses of tradition and modernity that were central to the nationalist debates in the late colonial era (Chatterjee 127). Her self-representation as a ruler is marked by an adherence to traditional norms combined with a reformative zeal, thereby striking a balance between both. For instance, she presents herself as a prudent ruler and pious Muslim, by writing about her reluctance to spend money lavishly for celebrations:

“I have always looked with disfavour on the superfluous ritual with which Muhammadans usually adorn their religious ceremonies, and I endeavour, as far as I can, to set an example of simplicity. On the present occasion, no ceremonial was observed which the laws of Islam do not strictly enjoin (188).

Here, as at other instances like her coronation, she marks herself as free of profligacy, which was a significant point of criticism against the princely rulers. She also adds that in this, she was following the steps of her mother and grandmother (Begam 209), thereby presenting her predecessors too as thrifty and wise rulers.

On the other hand, she also marks herself as a progressive sovereign by describing at length the reformative measures she introduced in Bhopal. Sultan Jahan places much emphasis on the field of education in her narrative and describes the schools she established, changes made to the existing curricula and steps taken to encourage her subjects to attend the educational institutions. Sultan Jahan Begam was a major figure in the reform efforts and women’s movements during her time, providing patronage and leadership for various associations working towards this end. She was the founding President of the All-India Muslim Ladies Conference, President of the All-India Women's Conference, patron of the National Council of Women in India (NCWI) and the founding Chancellor of Aligarh Muslim University, among others. In her autobiography, she appears particularly passionate about women’s education and notes:

Female education is a subject in which I take a deep interest, and I have always resented the unjust attitude which the sterner sex has adopted towards it. The idea of educating girls... had been limited to the teaching of the Quran and the rudiments of Urdu language...A girl’s education, if begun at all, should be carried far enough to produce some practical result, and, in addition to book learning should provide her with a

sufficient knowledge of household management and other feminine occupations to make her independent and happy in her future life " (323).

It can be noticed that the Begam expresses a practical as well as impassioned attitude towards female education. She remarks that she “resented” the “unjust” attitude of the “sterner sex” towards it, placing herself not as ruler, but as a woman who feels righteous anger against the unfairness meted out to her gender, empathising with them, though personally she herself was well-educated. It can also be noted that while the nationalist reformers’ declared intentions behind educating women were to make them better mothers and wives for the sake of a better family and society, the Begam’s emphasis is on making the girl “independent and happy” (Begam 323), i.e., for the sake of herself. More interestingly, she remarks that though this scheme of hers had opposers, they remained silent, partly because it had obvious advantages and “partly because it emanated from the ruler of the state” (324). While being aware of her power as a ruler, she is also vigilant not to provoke the conservatives among her subjects and devises means for making sure that the purdah system would not be violated while this project is implemented. The diplomacy she employs to meet her objectives while simultaneously making strategic compromises reveals that, in order to maintain stability, she initiated transformative changes incrementally, rather than mindlessly imposing her power which could result in a total backlash. This signifies a deeper understanding of the existing socio-political framework within which she efficiently negotiates her position as a female ruler.

Conclusion

In this article, I have examined how Sultan Jahan Begum drew on contemporary discourses to represent herself as a female sovereign in her autobiographical narrative. Building on the firm foundation of the familial legacy of female sovereignty, she further bolsters her position as a ruler by drawing upon the discourses of tradition, modernity, religion and colonialism, among

others, while simultaneously striking a balance between them to negotiate the inherent contradictions. This is further evident in her mode of representation that incorporates the modern autobiographical subject within the larger framework of Mughal imperial self-representation. *An Account of My Life* is, thus, a notable instance of a royal woman's self-fashioning through an advantageous utilisation of her position as sovereign, to redefine the prevailing dynamics between power and gender in a patriarchal society.

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